

CLASSIFICATION OF TOOLS AND EQUIPMENT IN INDUSTRIAL PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205359>

Abstract. You probably already know that the pharmaceutical industry is one of the most regulated and specialized globally. You need precision, accuracy, and rigorous adherence to quality standards throughout the pharmaceutical manufacturing, testing, and distribution processes. Having the proper machinery is essential for any pharmaceutical company.

Key words. *pharmaceutical industry, essential, investments, innovative development*

Introduction. The development of industrial pharmaceutical enterprises in the modern world is ahead of the curve, and pharmaceuticals is one of the most high-tech branches of the economy.

Thus, according to the results of research, turnover in the industrial sector of the pharmaceutical industry of the EU countries has increased to 1 trillion euros, the development strategy has its critics, since the prices of innovative drugs in the EU countries have risen sharply.

In general, healthcare spending in the EU is ahead of economic growth, as pharmaceuticals are science-intensive, and innovative medicines are becoming more expensive even for developed countries.

The policy of the European Union countries is aimed at making investments in the innovative development of the pharmaceutical industry. Representatives of pharmaceutical companies are convinced that the price increase is justified. Analysts currently estimate that 1.9 billion is needed to bring a new drug to the market euro.

Therefore, industry research funding in Europe, according to the Center for Drug Development Research in Boston, reaches more than 30.9 billion euros - approximately 3% of total revenue. The pharmaceutical sector of EU countries benefits economically from advanced research and development facilities, long traditions in production and a diversified system of large corporations, as well as small and medium-sized enterprises. Together, they form scientific and industrial clusters that create a solid base for providing necessary professional knowledge

to masters of pharmacy, solving the problems of the global health care market, influencing modernization changes in the content of higher pharmaceutical education.

The global demand for pharmaceuticals is constantly increasing due to the growth of the world population and demographic changes. Along with significant scientific advances, especially in the field of medical biotechnology, scientific developments provide a boost to the pharmaceutical industry worldwide. The medical and pharmaceutical industry has turned into one of the most important levers of global growth in Europe.

According to IMS Health, global spending on the development of the pharmaceutical sector in 2021 will amount to 1.5 trillion dollars. and, to a large extent, due to the introduction of industry innovations, which is best evidenced by the high number of new approved medicinal products in the EU countries. More than 400 new pharmaceuticals – an average of 37 per year – are authorized by the European Medicines Agency for the European Union.

Innovative in the development of the pharmaceutical industry in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe is the international cooperation in the field of pharmaceutical science and practice with 16 main German industry associations and is part of the MITTELSTAND GLOBAL program for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Technological developments such as digitization and industrial projects are also modernizing the pharmaceutical sector and healthcare management. This offers great potential for more efficient research and development, as computational, high through put approaches help improve the analysis of large databases.

Aspects of digitization include the introduction of real-time online monitoring in pharmaceutical manufacturing plants, related manufacturing processes and increased automation of industrial value chains in the sector. With its strong tradition in engineering and plant construction, as well as its expertise in pharmaceutical chemistry, Germany offers the ideal infrastructure for combining cost-effective, IT based innovation with traditional, high-quality manufacturing processes. At the beginning of the 21st century, new trends began to develop - Eco pharmacy and social pharmacy. They combine the goal of creating high-quality, safe and affordable medicines for patients.

Innovation in the pharmaceutical sector is largely driven by technological advances in molecular and cellular biology. New technologies and research tools based on these findings pave the way for a better understanding of disorders and

enable new strategies to combat not only the symptoms, but also the actual causes of the pathologies.

High-quality pharmaceutical equipment plays a vital role in overall product quality and compliance with FDA regulations. Machine manufacturers can tailor production systems down to the last detail to ensure every capsule, tablet, and liquid is manufactured exactly to every applicable standard.

Customized pharmaceutical equipment allows facilities to produce goods faster and with fewer manual processes to slow down production or introduce unwanted variables. Not only will up-to-date equipment standardize processes ranging from raw material preparation to dispensing and packaging, but automation also drives greater long-term profitability.

In the increasingly fast-paced U.S. pharmaceutical industry, companies that remain updated on the latest best practices and equipment are undergoing significant growth. Six of the global top 10 pharma companies (based on revenue) are based in the United States, where between 2015 and 2018, the industry saw an average of 10% annual growth and sales of more than \$400 billion per year.

Key market benefits of regularly updating or customizing pharmaceutical equipment include:

More precise testing and analysis. Production facilities rely on advanced equipment to identify potentially flawed samples and alert operators of possible errors. Pharmaceutical laboratories also use analysis equipment to observe test results, better monitor specimen reactions, improve production speeds, and create better products for end-users.

Reduce costs for the facility and for customers. Smarter, more streamlined equipment cuts down on manual tasks and wasted materials. Making production methods more efficient reduces facility costs and the total cost per product. These savings can result in higher profits, savings for customers, and more. Lowering the price of pharmaceutical production ultimately helps facilitate broader access to the critical medicine patients need.

When sourcing a contract manufacturer for your pharmaceutical products, consider the following:

Quality. Seek a respected manufacturer with a proven record of delivering high-quality equipment.

Volume and speed. Make sure the manufacturer can deliver equipment that meets your specifications for volume and production time. These requirements will depend on the specific products you're synthesizing and whether you're producing them for commercial or research purposes.

Physical product needs. Different products will have different process requirements for heating, cooling, drying, and more. Ensure that you purchase equipment that meets all of these needs.

Computer processing abilities. High-end computer systems can improve manufacturing processes and make equipment easier to operate.

Ease of cleaning. The simpler your equipment is to disconnect, the easier it will be to clean. Easy cleaning saves valuable production time.

There are multiple types of equipment involved in pharmaceutical manufacturing, such as:

Centrifuges to separate liquids from solids, as well as for separating liquids of varying densities from one another.

Cooling towers for condensing steam and cooling liquids.

Dryers to dry out liquids and making them into powders.

Granulators for turning powders into granules.

Capsuling equipment for filling and polishing capsules.

Coating machines to coat capsules and tablets with sugar and other films.

Inspection equipment to examine products for accuracy and consistency as they move through production.

Pharmaceutical machines must adhere to some of the strictest guidelines of any machinery used in business today. That's why computer numeric control (CNC) machining processes are so crucial to the successful fabrication of pharmaceutical equipment. The vast majority of machinery used in pharmaceutical manufacturing relies on CNC machining, such as:

Blending equipment

Capsule equipment

Centrifuges

Coating machines

Cooling towers

Dryers

Filling equipment

Granulators

Hot melt extrusion equipment

Inspection machines

Milling machines

Processing machinery

Tablet presses

CNC machining processes use standardized, encoded procedures to direct each piece of manufacturing equipment. This process ensures that every machining and fabrication step is accurate, precise, and methodical. It also guarantees that every production process is repeatable down to the last detail and verifiable by advanced monitoring and testing equipment.

Modern manufacturing equipment can handle more complex tasks autonomously than ever before. Well-designed modern pharmaceutical machinery and components have greatly improved pharmaceutical manufacturing by reducing mistakes, lowering maintenance requirements, limiting waste, and streamlining production efficiency.

At Astro Machine Works, we have the in-house expertise and fully equipped facility to deliver finely detailed pharmaceutical equipment and replacement parts—all while meeting Current Good Manufacturing Practice (CGMP) regulations under the FDA's latest guidelines.

Although the CNC process has existed since the late 1960s, all of the materials we work with and the components we produce are state-of-the-art. Our expertise in automated precision machining has been refined over many decades of operation. From our top-notch customer service representatives to our first-rate engineers and machinists, our team is all about delivering precision and value.

With millions of dollars on the line with each run, pharmaceutical manufacturers can't afford a bad production day. It's important to partner with an equipment manufacturer that appreciates what's at stake for your business and can deliver both custom work and cost-effective solutions, greatly increasing your ability to remain competitive in the pharmaceutical market.

Our 72,000-square foot facility in Ephrata, Pennsylvania was specifically designed to create an efficient workflow for our team of skilled professionals to produce innovative pharmaceutical equipment and parts. That's why our clients trust us with their most important machining and manufacturing needs. Our services include:

Precision CNC machining (lathing/turning, grinding, milling)

Wire EDM

Custom machine building

Procurement of raw materials and components

Equipment testing and debugging

Reverse engineering of machinery and components

Welding and fabrication

Machine repairs, rebuilds, and refurbishment

Conclusion. In conclusion we may say that, the classification of tools and equipment in industrial pharmaceutical production enterprises and personalized medicine has also become a new trend and a basis for the implementation of targeted and rational pharmacotherapy.

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